

Redshift Quantization Phenomenon described by an Elementary Quantum Gravity Model

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- Preprint -

Abstract

Although gravitation as described by Newton is an elementary force, gravity constant G is still the least precisely known in physics. Moreover, despite significant effort spend over more than half a century, a coherent and effective theory of quantum gravity has not yet been derived.

At the same time a phenomenon called redshift quantization observed in gas spectra from galaxies and quasar structures has been empirically described with increasing evidence based on broader and more refined statistical methodologies, however the effect partially is still disputed.

In this article I derive an analytical Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM) comprising quantum energy states and quantum exchange particles. Based on this, gravitational quantum effects between mass objects are proposed, and an analytical explanation for the Redshift Quantization phenomenon is given. The approach delivers significant analytical qualitative and quantitative agreement with observed redshift peaks in the range of $\Delta z = 0.001 \dots 3.6$, and for peaks at $\Delta z = 1.95$, as well as at $\Delta z = 0.061 \dots 0.063$.

Key words: quantum gravity, quantum cosmology, alternative gravity theories, redshift quantization

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I. INTRODUCTION

To date the gravitational force between two mass objects is described by Newton's law [1] as first confirmed in measurement by Henry Cavendish in the 18th century [2]:

$$F_g = \frac{m_1 m_2 G}{r^2}. \quad (1)$$

Since then, it has been tried to describe its nature, leading to general relativity theory of A. Einstein in the 20th century, as a geometric approach on space-time [3]. Although discovered more than three centuries ago, G is still the most imprecisely determined constant in physics [4], with $G = 6.6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-2}$ and a relative uncertainty of $2.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$.

Moreover, despite intense and diverse attempts to link gravity and quantum mechanics over the last decades, leading to several competing approaches, none of them proves so far to resolve major inconsistencies qualitatively and quantitatively observed with gravitation in nature. Overviews reflecting the state of research can be found for example in [5], [6], [7].

In this article a model to gain new insights into the quantization of gravity is derived. I follow the approach, that it should be as simple as possible, only as complicated as necessary, and in line with proven observations and physical models.

II. ELEMENTARY QUANTUM GRAVITY MODEL (EQGM)

Following the aim of this article, I use proven quantum mechanical laws and models to compose an Elementary Quantum Gravity Model (EQGM).

A. Quantum mechanical approach

Introducing quantum mechanics, I start with a one-dimensional Heisenberg uncertainty [8] with $x=r$ to address a radially symmetric Universe and adapt it with the Lorentz factor γ to consider relativistic effects.

Hence, the variance of momentum and location, as well as of energy and time for a mass object all must have non-zero values. With the reduced Planck quantum of action

$\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$ and $h = 6.62607015 \cdot 10^{-34} \text{ J}$ it writes:

$$\sigma_p \sigma_x \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_w \sigma_t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (2)$$

I apply this to a mass object (mo) in the Universe (U). The

radius of the Universe is confining the location of the object in a gravitational potential well, while the time uncertainty is related to the time in the Universe. The same approach can also be applied to other gravitational potential wells like for example galaxies or black holes.

In the relativistic view, in principle for a mass object its energy uncertainty can be rooted in its kinetic energy and/or in its rest energy.

To formulate the EQGM I will make use of the fundamental Planck-units, as introduced in the year 1899 for basic physical quantities [9]. They are composed only of key constants determining relativistic electrodynamics (speed of light $c_0 = 2.99792458 \cdot 10^8 \text{ m/s}$), gravitation (gravity constant G), and quantum mechanics (quantum of action \hbar). Furthermore Planck-units describe a limit for quantum effects in gravitation, while Planck-mass can be found in setting the Schwarzschild perimeter of a black hole to be equal to its Compton wavelength [10]:

$$2\pi r_s = \lambda_c \quad \text{with} \quad r_s = \frac{m_{pl} G}{c_0^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \lambda_c = \frac{\hbar}{m_{pl} c_0}, \quad \text{yielding:}$$

$$m_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0}{G}} = 2.178 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ kg}. \quad \text{Moreover Planck-length}$$

$$\text{defined as: } l_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c_0^3}} = 1.616 \cdot 10^{-35} \text{ m}, \quad \text{resulting to Planck-}$$

$$\text{time for light traveling along it: } t_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c_0^5}} = 5.391 \cdot 10^{-44} \text{ s},$$

and the Planck-energy, exhibiting a value of rest energy

$$\text{for Planck-mass: } W_{pl} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c_0^5}{G}} = m_{pl} c_0^2 = 1.956 \cdot 10^9 \text{ J}.$$

B. Quantization of gravitation

To describe interaction between two mass objects I use an analogy to proven laws from atom and solid-state physics, namely the quantum model for an electron in the Coulomb potential of a hydrogen atom. This has been found by N. Bohr more than a century ago and explains the stability of atoms due to finite and quantized energy levels arising, despite a hyperbolic singularity potential [11]. Bohr's postulate:

$$pr \equiv \hbar n, \quad \text{with: } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (3)$$

is a discretized Heisenberg uncertainty, equaling integer multiples of Planck's quantum of action with the product of momentum and location.

1. Non-relativistic case

With this, quantized energies and radii were obtained for the electron in the hydrogen atom:

$$W_{qC} = \frac{-q^2}{8\pi\epsilon_0 r_B n^2} \text{ and Bohr radius: } r_B = \frac{4\pi\epsilon_0 \hbar^2}{m_e q^2}. \quad (4)$$

I transfer this to a model for gravitation between mass objects. Since Coulomb and gravitation force laws are similar related to the formula above, except for a factor $G/(8\pi\epsilon_0)$ and charge q^2 to be replaced by the product of mass m and M , we gain:

$$W_{qspot} = \frac{-mMG}{r_{gB} n^2} = \frac{-m^3 M^2 G^2}{\hbar^2 n^2} = -W_{kin}, \quad (5)$$

and a “gravitational Bohr radius”:

$$r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar^2}{m^2 MG} \quad (6)$$

In the three-dimensional spherical Bohr atom model, each energy state n can be occupied with a maximum of $2n^2$ fermionic mass objects, hence resulting to a total number of quantum states available of $2n^3$. Hence N mass objects confined in a sphere with radius R will occupy the states up to the highest kinetic energy known as the Fermi energy [12] adding on top of the zero-point energy level:

$$W_F = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \left(\frac{3\pi^2 N}{(4/3)\pi R^3} \right)^{\frac{2}{3}}. \quad (7)$$

2. Ultra-relativistic case

A relativistic Bohr postulate with the Lorentz factor to consider increase of inertia in the inertial system of the Universe (U) and contraction of length in the inertial system of the mass object (m_0) on the circular trajectory to meet the quantization criteria is set up:

$$p_U r_{m_0} = m\gamma v_U r_U \gamma^{-1} \equiv \hbar n,$$

with the Lorentz factor [13] given as:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c_0^2}}}. \quad (8)$$

For the velocity of the mass object, it is gained from the formula for relativistic kinetic energy:

$$W_{kin} = (\gamma - 1)mc_0^2, \text{ thus}$$

$$v_U = c_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \beta)^2}}, \text{ with: } \beta = \frac{W_{kin}}{mc_0^2}. \quad (9)$$

After simplification for the ultra-relativistic regime with $\beta \gg 1$ this yields for the relativistic gravitational Bohr radius of the mass object m within the inertial system of the Universe and for the kinetic energy of mass:

$$r_{gB} = \frac{\hbar}{mc_0} = \tilde{\lambda}_C \text{ and } W_{kin} = \frac{m^2 MGc_0}{n\hbar}. \quad (10)$$

With $\tilde{\lambda}_C = \frac{\hbar}{mc_0}$ being the reduced Compton wavelength

for a mass object m , meaning that its rest energy equals the energy of a photon with this wavelength. This is also known as minimum size for which a reasonable radius of a mass object can be defined due to quantum uncertainty.

For the case $\beta = 1$, i.e. with the Lorentz factor assuming the value of two, it results¹: $r_{gB} = \frac{2\hbar}{\sqrt{3}mc_0}$, and for the kinetic

$$\text{energy: } W_{kin} = \frac{\sqrt{3}m^2 MGc_0}{2n\hbar}.$$

Reformulating Eq. (10), I find an expression that can be interpreted as containing a quantum exchange particle I call “Ghton” (Gh)² in analogy to a Photon since it seems to be moving with the speed of light:

$$W_{kin} = \frac{(mc_0^2)^2}{n_{Gr} W_{Gh}} = W_{Gr}(n_{Gr}), \text{ with:}$$

¹ This contains the minimum gravitational coupling parameter: $\alpha_{Gzp} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} = 0.866$; for derivation refer to [23]. For the ultra-relativistic regime $\beta \gg 1$ it is: $\alpha_{Gzp} \rightarrow 1$.

² The Ghton can also be found for the non-relativistic case in reformulating Eq. (5) above:

$$-W_{qspot} = \frac{mMG}{r_{gB} n^2} = \frac{m^3 M^2 G^2}{\hbar^2 n^2} = \frac{(mc_0^2)^3}{n_{Gr}^2 W_{Gh}^2} = W_{kin} = W_{Gr}(n_{Gr}).$$

$$W_{Gh} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{\left[\frac{GM}{c_0^2}\right]} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{\left[\frac{r_S}{2}\right]} = \frac{\hbar c_0}{r_g} . \quad (11)$$

For the quantized energy state levels, I call these quasi-particles ‘‘Gravons’’ (Gr), with n_{Gr} the Gravon quantum number. This is in analogy to the Phonon, the quasi-particle for the energy states of collective atom oscillations in solid-state crystals [12].

From Eq. (11) the denominator is half of the Schwarzschild radius for a non-rotating black hole made up by mass M , or the Schwarzschild aka gravitational radius for a rotating black hole [14]. Furthermore Eq. (11) divided by the speed of light yields the de Broglie [15] expression with the gravitational perimeter of a rotating black hole as the wavelength.

3. General relativistic case

The complete derivation of the hyperbolic gravitational potential for the relativistic case is obtained based on Eq. (8) and Eq. (9), plus the condition according to the Bohr atom model that gravitational and centrifugal force must compensate at the mass object:

$$F_g = \frac{m\gamma MG}{r_U^2} \equiv \frac{mv_U^2}{r_U} = F_c \quad (12)$$

Reformatting Eq. (8) and Eq. (12) to v_U and combining

them delivers $r_U = \frac{\hbar^2 n^2}{m^2 MG \gamma}$, and again with Eq. (8)

yields: $v_U = \frac{mMG\gamma}{\hbar n} = \frac{mMG}{\hbar n \sqrt{1 - v_U^2 / c_0^2}}$, a bi-quadratic

equation for v_U . It shows to have two solutions for

$v_U < c_0$:

$$v_{U1/2} = \frac{c_0}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{1 \pm \sqrt{1 - 4 \left(\frac{mMG}{\hbar n c_0} \right)^2}} \quad (13)$$

However, in the hyperbolic potential v must approach zero for quantum numbers n and distance between m and M approaching infinity, which is the case for the solution with the negative sign. While the second radicand behind the sign is non-negative for:

$$n \geq n_s = \frac{2mMG}{\hbar c_0} = \frac{2MG}{c_0^2 \tilde{\chi}_C(m)} = \frac{r_s}{\tilde{\chi}_C(m)} = \frac{r_s}{r_{gBr}} \quad (14)$$

This means beyond certain values of mass product constellations (mM), where the relativistic gravitational Bohr radius as derived in Eq. (10) is less than the

Schwarzschild radius r_s of M , the center of mass object m is located within the black hole for quantum numbers below n_s . Thus, the two solutions \pm of Eq. (13) describe the center of object m being outside the black hole (-) versus inside (+). For the case outside the black hole i.e., solution (-) it is $v_U < c_0 / \sqrt{2}$ realizing this value coming from high quantum numbers towards the minimum possible n_s . For lower values of n , complex velocity values will result. To obtain a real meaning from this, the absolute relativistic kinetic energy needs to be calculated as:

$$W_{kr}(m) = |\gamma - 1| m c_0^2 . \quad (15)$$

For the solution (+) and increasing values of $n > n_s$ i.e., within the black hole, it evolves: $v_U \rightarrow c_0$. However, the (+) solution will not be followed-up here, thus it remains unclear whether it has any real meaning.

C. Approach to Redshift Quantization

With the EQGM an explanation for the redshift quantization phenomenon in the spectrum of hydrogen atoms observed in some galaxies and quasar structures shall be given. To date the phenomenon is not yet understood and partially still disputed.

More than half a century ago, astronomical observations of electromagnetic spectrums – e.g. the 21 cm hydrogen line - delivered redshift results with different peak values and discretization increments in the order of magnitude $\Delta z = 0.001 \dots 3.6$, with $\Delta z = 1.95$, as well as $\Delta z = 0.061 \dots 0.063$, and periodic multiples of the latter one being prominent values reported – see [16], [17], [18], [19]. The redshift quantization is hypothesized to be intrinsic to galaxies and quasars, but with origins unknown so far. Thus, it is not considered to be related to cosmological redshift due to Hubble expansion.

To obtain such high redshift values from quantized gravitational fields, the hydrogen atoms observed must be moving with fractions of the speed of light i.e., close to massive objects M , if not even black holes. Furthermore, such obvious discretization can only occur at low quantum numbers, since otherwise continuum effects for the redshift would apply. The combination of these two aspects leads to the conclusion that the radius – see Eq. (10) - for the free hydrogen atom mass m_n observed around M must be in the range of some femtometers.

Hence, possible candidates for M could be Primordial Black Holes (PBH) emerged out of fluctuations in the early Universe, as described by S. Hawking in [20]. Such

black holes would have to exhibit a minimum mass according to their Schwarzschild radius to be equal or larger than the reduced Compton wavelength of the particles - as related to their relativistic energy including rest energy - constituting such black hole. These constituents could be neutrons and/or protons, or pairs of them, thus deuterons. In the latter case this allows for less minimum mass required to compose a PBH as compared to protons/neutrons alone. Hawking also concluded that these objects may carry of up to $Z < 30$ Coulomb charges. Thus, the mass of such PBH would be:

$$M_{pbhdc} = \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_C(m_{con})c_0^2}{2G} = 6.72110^{10} \text{ kg} , \text{ with the effective}$$

constituent particle mass $m_{con} = m_n + m_p - \Delta m_{md} + \Delta m_C = 2.107 m_n$, i.e. made up by the mass of the deuteron containing the neutron and proton minus the mass defect of their binding energy $\Delta m_{md} = 2.222 \text{ MeV } c_0^{-2}$, plus the mass equivalent of the potential Coulomb energy for an average charge: Here I do assume the average as $Z = 15$:

$$\Delta m_C = \left(\frac{Zq^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\tilde{\lambda}_C(m_p)} \right) c_0^{-2} .$$

Eq. (13) reveals another property of such PBH: In addition to its minimum required mass M_{pbhdc} , this is also the maximum value for mass, if the PBH was grown out of nucleons and/or hydrogen. This is since the ground state $n = 1$ and related minimum radius for hydrogen atoms and H_2 molecules being gravitationally attracted by the PBH is the lowest possible. For this case Eq. (14) delivers $n_S < 1$, i.e., all quantum levels are located outside the PBH so that hydrogen atoms and H_2 molecules cannot fall into and grow the PBH further. This gives rise to the assumption, that only integer multiples of the PBH mass appear in some regions of the galaxies and quasar objects. In the further process these PBHs with exact mass M_{pbhdc} would attract each other to merge into larger black holes.

The intrinsic redshift formula for mass objects moving with velocity v in the inertial system of a galaxy - without consideration of the recessional aka cosmological redshift of the galaxy in the Universe - can be found for example in [14]: $z_{int} = z_t + z_g$ for transverse Doppler redshift, and $z_{inr} = z_r + z_g$ for radial Doppler redshift, respectively, while in each the gravitational aka Einstein redshift z_g has to be considered as well. In this it is $z_g = |\gamma - 1|$ and $z_t = |\gamma - 1|$, while γ being the Lorentz factor, and

$$z_r = \sqrt{\frac{1 + \frac{v}{c_0}}{1 - \frac{v}{c_0}}} - 1 .$$

To calculate the redshift, Eq. (13) and Eq. (15) are used for the hydrogen atom with mass m_n in the hyperbolic gravitational potential of charged PBHs with $M_x = jM_{pbhdc}$ and $j \in \mathbb{N}$:

$$W_{kr}(n, j, m) = mc_0^2 |\gamma(n, j, m) - 1| , \text{ and:}$$

$$\gamma(n, j, m) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\sqrt{1 + \sqrt{1 - 4 \left(\frac{mjM_{pbhdc}G}{\hbar nc_0} \right)^2}}}} , \quad (16)$$

which can be rewritten to:

$$\gamma(n, j, m) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\sqrt{1 + \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{j}{n} \frac{2mM_{pbhdc}}{m_{pl}^2} \right)^2}}}} . \quad (17)$$

From the Lorentz formula and Eq. (17) also v can be calculated as:

$$v(n, j, m) = c_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{\gamma(n, j, m)^2}} . \quad (18)$$

With Eq. (18) and Eq. (8) it is gained for the radius aka distance of the mass center from the center of the black hole:

$$r_U(n, j, m) = \frac{\hbar n}{mv} . \quad (19)$$

Thus, the ground-state radius for hydrogen atoms at a PBH with M_{pbhdc} is 0.859 fm . For very large j , i.e. large black holes from merged PBHs, the ground-state radius at $n = 1$ for any mass m approaches $r_{U\infty} \rightarrow \tilde{\lambda}_C(m) / \alpha_{Gzp} = 2r_{gBr}(m) / \sqrt{3}$, i.e. for hydrogen atoms this is 0.243 fm . Note that the radius of the hydrogen atom as such including its electron is more than five orders of magnitude larger, however this shall not prevent the PBH and hydrogen atom core gravitational interaction to exist.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since mass objects do mostly differ, in the EQGM this offsets the minimum energy level for each value of mass as can be seen from Eq. (10) for the Gravon energy. Moreover, the Universe appears only homogeneous at scale, but is made of clusters of galaxies, solar systems, stars, planets, dust, gas, etc. as local structures, all of them representing gravitational potential wells.

This leads to coupled potentials of different size. Superposition of quantum states can be assumed to lead to split-up of energy states into quasi-continua for objects being in proximity, as this is well-known for electrons in the coulomb potentials within solid-state crystals. Concluding, we can assume that every mass object is finding an unoccupied energy state in the current Universe.

Quantization effects in the motion of mass objects may become obvious under some circumstances – like in Redshift Quantization, but not be perceived due to tiny Ghoton energies between Gravons and/or continuum effects in most other cases.

A. Gravitational quantum particles and matter waves

First gravitational particles were assumed by Pierre-Simon Laplace more than two centuries ago, while a quantum mechanical particle named Graviton was mentioned around the mid-20th century. In the diverse set of quantum gravity approaches the Graviton is mostly, but not always, assumed to be the exchange quantum of gravitation. However, also further particles were proposed, like Gravitino, Goldstino, Sgoldstino, Gravissskalar and Gravitvektor [21].

In the EQGM each mass object has a quantized gravitational energy state – dubbed with the quasi-particle name “Gravon” – and a de Broglie matter wave [15] associated. The gravitational effect is assumed to be realized via the quantum exchange particle dubbed Ghoton, moving at the speed of light. For a mass object to change its gravitational energy i.e., Gravon state, Ghotons have to be emitted to decrease, or absorbed to increase its gravitational energy, respectively.

Both, Ghoton and Gravon, quantum particle energies are inversely proportional to the confinement space, thus the distance between interacting mass objects.

Regarding gravitational coupling significant effects must be expected due to relativistic kinetic zero-point energy of mass in the Universe - see derivation of the quantum gravitational coupling parameter in the Appendix.

To conclude, in the EQGM the Ghoton is the exchange particle to play the role of the Graviton, while the Gravon is a quasi-particle representing the matter waves.

B. Analysis of Redshift Quantization

In this section the approach for quantum gravity and redshift quantization is applied and analyzed.

Assuming that in galaxies the values for the PBHs mass range from $j = 1..j_{\max}$ (number of merged PBHs attracting hydrogen atoms whose spectra are observed) and $n = 1..n_{\max}$ (gravitational quantum states occupied by hydrogen atoms around the black hole) may vary, different sets of discretized redshifts may be observed.

Fig. 1 and 2 display the transverse and radial Doppler redshifts including gravitational redshift for hydrogen atoms occupying all quantum levels of 1..20 in the quantized field of a black hole, and with equally distributed mass values of integer multiples from $1..10^4 M_{pbhdc}$ PBH mass constituted out of deuterons and with 15 Coulomb charges each³. Tab. 1 and 2 contain the redshift values for the 8 lowest quantum levels and PBH mass multiples of the black hole, respectively.

FIG. 1. Relative probability of transverse Doppler (circles) and radial Doppler (crosses) redshift values z and including gravitational Einstein redshift for hydrogen atoms occupying quantum levels of up to $n_{\max} = 20$ in the gravitational fields of black holes with masses of up to $10^4 M_{pbhdc}$ and a Coulomb charge of $Z = 15$ each constituted of deuterons. The bin width for

³ Note, that due to Hawking radiation black holes do evaporate after a certain time, if no infalling matter is compensating the loss of mass. Such complete evaporation over the lifetime of the Universe may happen for $M_{pbh} < 4..5 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ kg}$; see [22], i.e., for less than ten PBH mass $j < 10$.

z statistics is chosen to be 0.001.

FIG. 2. Same content as in FIG. 1, but with a focus on and zoom-in to the lower end of the redshift z-axis.

From Eq. (17) with the mass m of hydrogen atoms a characteristic value of $z_{\text{int}} = 0.063$ is very prominent⁴, because it appears for all combinations (j, n) with $j = n$ so that the quotient is $j/n = 1$. This is the most common value for the quotient out of the set of integer combinations – see also Figures 1 and 2. Moreover, integer values of the quotient are prominent since they have a periodic appearance as compared to non-integer fractions. This may explain the observed periodicity of $\Delta z = 0.063$ described in some of the references – see for example [16], [18], [19].

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	0.063	0.467	0.933	1.002	1.086	1.140	1.184	1.222
2	0.014	0.063	0.168	0.467	0.879	0.933	0.98	1.02
3	0.006	0.026	0.063	0.123	0.228	0.467	0.858	0.898
4	0.004	0.014	0.034	0.063	0.105	0.168	0.267	0.467
5	0.002	0.009	0.021	0.039	0.063	0.095	0.14	0.201
6	0.002	0.006	0.014	0.026	0.042	0.063	0.089	0.123
7	0.001	0.005	0.011	0.019	0.03	0.045	0.063	0.085
8	0.001	0.004	0.008	0.014	0.023	0.034	0.047	0.063

TAB. 1. Transverse Doppler redshift values for hydrogen atoms including gravitational redshift at the first 8 quantum levels (vertical direction) with black holes exhibiting multiples of 1.8 PBH mass (horizontal direction).

For hydrogen atoms, the characteristic value around $z_{\text{int}} = 1.96$ allows to conclude on the average mass

⁴ In the initial publication of Karlsson on „Possible Quantization of Quasar Redshifts” [17] the characteristic observed peak values are stated as $z = 0.061, 0.06$, while calculating from his fit formula $(1 - z_i)/(1 + z_{i+1}) = 1.227$, and $z_1 = 1.956$, this results to: $z_2 = 1.409$, $z_3 = 0.963$, $z_4 = 0.6$, $z_5 = 0.304$, and $z_6 = 0.063$.

multiples of merged PBHs. This value indicates around 10^4 PBHs merged. For the number of merged PBHs towards infinity it would result $\gamma \rightarrow 0$, hence: $z_{\text{int}} \rightarrow 2$, since $z_g \rightarrow 1$ and $z_i \rightarrow 1$.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	0.315	1.189	2.006	2.151	2.261	2.350	2.423	2.484
2	0.135	0.315	0.586	1.189	1.914	2.006	2.084	2.151
3	0.086	0.189	0.315	0.48	0.719	1.189	1.880	1.947
4	0.063	0.135	0.218	0.315	0.434	0.586	0.8	1.189
5	0.05	0.105	0.166	0.236	0.315	0.408	0.52	0.661
6	0.041	0.086	0.135	0.189	0.248	0.315	0.391	0.48
7	0.035	0.073	0.113	0.157	0.205	0.257	0.315	0.38
8	0.031	0.063	0.098	0.135	0.175	0.218	0.264	0.315

TAB. 2. Radial Doppler redshift values for hydrogen atoms including gravitational redshift at the first 8 quantum levels (vertical direction) with black holes exhibiting multiples 1..8 of PBH mass (horizontal direction).

The characteristic value around $z_{\text{int}} = 3.6$ is also due to an average of around 10^4 merged PBHs. For the number of merged PBHs towards infinity it would result to:

$$z_{\text{int}} \rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{1 + \sqrt{3}/2}{1 - \sqrt{3}/2}} + z_g = 3.732, \text{ since with Eq. (9) from}$$

$$\text{with } z_g \rightarrow 1 \text{ and } \beta = z_g \text{ it is: } v \rightarrow c_0 \sqrt{\frac{3}{4}}.$$

For higher numbers of occupied quantum level states n , up to $n_{\text{max}} \rightarrow \infty$, more redshift values in the range of $z \rightarrow 0$ will appear. Hence also in galaxies with high gas hydrogen density the discretized redshift with prominent values as shown in Fig. 1 could be observed.

Furthermore, since in the redshift formula Eq. (17) the product (mM_{pbhdc}) is relevant, larger characteristic values for z will result for the redshifted spectrum received from larger mass observed in the gravitational field of the black holes. For example, the prominent values for transverse Doppler including gravitational redshift for OH molecules would result to 1.416, for CO₂ to 1.61, and for H₂ to 0.467, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The relatively simple EQGM looking at the Universe as composed of quantum wells delivers qualitative and quantitative explanation approaches for Redshift Quantization, as being rooted in quantum gravity. It delivers analytical derivations and explanations for discretization in line with prominent peak values observed. Furthermore, it reveals an indication for the existence and pivotal role of Primordial Black Holes (PBH) in the Universe.

Moreover, it is found that gravity can be described as a quantum mechanical effect due to confinement of mass objects.

Given the vast diversity and history of research in the field of quantum gravity done in the last decades, it must be beyond the scope of this work to discuss and assess the EQGM as compared to the variety of approaches.

Since quantum gravity should exhibit discrete effects also in other contexts, further study should be applied. Some preliminary further considerations can be found in [23].

Note: The procedure scripts used for calculation of the Redshift Quantization figures and tables above can be obtained from the author upon request.

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